

Power architecture in Modern New Zealand

From its establishment in 1948, the Hydroelectric Design Office (HDO) of the New Zealand Ministry of Works developed an architectural response to the country's technological experience of modernity, as evidenced in a national electrification plan. The projects of this office are individually resolved power stations, occupying specific sites on major waterways, and while it is possible to treat them as discrete architectural and engineering works, it is equally possible to discuss them as nodes in a national 'grid'. In this latter sense, widely held ideas on electrification are important prefaces to the architect's experience of designing for hydroelectric production; the monumentality of power station sites, while a consequence of the engineering involved in electricity production, provides a fitting legacy for the ideology attached to these national endeavours. Power stations trace a point in New Zealand's history at which electricity was essential; further, they index a mechanism of production and consumption in which landscape is rendered both cultural and modern, a resource for rapidly expanding industrial and urban, albeit relatively distant, cities. This development, and the role these sites played in that process, was recognisably one of modernisation. It was the means to fulfil widely held demands for electric transport systems, street lighting, telephones, and complete access by domestic consumers to public electricity supply. Architects involved in power station design therefore became complicit in an architecture conveying electricity's significance to an increasingly modernised country.

From the first instance of public electricity supply in 1879, energy production sites represented for the Government a chance to unify a sparsely populated country, and to gain international recognition as a modern country. Two strategies were set out: New Zealand would grow smaller through commu-

nication devices and networks (such as rail and telegraph); and it would become less remote as an exporter, sending dairy produce home to the United Kingdom. In each case, electricity played an important role: networks in the first instance, refrigeration in the second. From 1918, Chief Electrical Engineer Evan Parry made declarations that mimicked the spirit of the Soviets, establishing an uncompromising programme of complete electrical reticulation. In order to cover the demands of urban centres, the rural population, and industrial development, power needed to be generated from a small number of significantly productive sites, predominantly hydroelectric, and distributed through an interconnected system. This would comprise "one of the most essential agents in national reconstruction." (Martin, 1998: 68) The campaign targeted each individual; the more remote, the more assistance they deserved.

The Ministry's antecedent, the Public Works Department maintained a close control of electrification and systems put in place across the country were essentially universal. This reflected a singularity of purpose for both the Government and its agencies. Established in 1945, the Rural Electrification Reticulation Council (RERC) systematically connected the isolated seven per cent of the population over a short period, focussing effort particularly on rural dwellers in more remote areas. This effort saw public supply reach into homes, businesses, farms, factories, and streets of 99.8 per cent of New Zealanders, exceeding the results of any other national scheme. As demand increased, a vigorous construction programme adding productive sites to the national framework staved off widespread electricity shortage through the mid-1940s. In the North Island, New Zealand's longest river, the Waikato, suggested many potential dam sites. In the South Island, engineers targeted the Waitaki and Clutha Rivers for development of their high volumes and extensive catchment areas.

Establishment of the HDO followed a general reorganisation of public works agencies in 1948 under the more responsible control of the Ministry of Works. The Office permanently seconded a small team of architects and draughtsmen from the Government Architect's staff to work with civil and electrical engineering specialists; as a multi-disciplinary team, it was responsible for all aspects of the civil, mechanical, and architectural design of hydroelectric projects. The first architectural Section Head was the Viennese Frederick H. Newman (1900-1964), who immigrated to New Zealand with his extended family as a refugee in 1938. Educated in Vienna and Paris, he had earlier joined the large contingent of German and Austrian architects who fol-

lowed Ernst May to Moscow in the 1930s, working from 1932-1937 on architectural projects that bolstered the infrastructure and administrative capacities both of new cities and existing industrial settlements.¹ He worked in the Department of Housing Construction from 1939 until 1948 and the formation of the HDO. Newman's writing on the architect's role in nationally important building programmes reveals some of the ideological and architectural thinking behind aesthetic and material choices in the HDO's architecture programme. Discursively, it is quite possible to briefly consider this programme as distinct from the important pragmatic concerns shared by the engineering profession in this context. In the design of "cathedrals of power," Newman dealt with the dual pursuits his work required as both an architectural expression of electricity and the exploration of an appropriate technical response to the architecture of electricity. (Newman, 1959: 80) It forced Newman to consider the role of architects productively involved in large-scale engineering works; his response to this challenge resulted in his assumption of the task of communicating power to a nation. On this matter he wrote:

"The national importance of these large structures must, I repeat, must, find architectural expression. It is imperative that these works become cultural assets because they are part of our social life. Production of power – though their primary function – is not all that matters." (Newman, 1959: 70)

In setting out the parameters of the architect's influence in this programme, Newman considered the skills and attitudes an architect would constructively contribute to an engineer's work. As in the design offices of the Tennessee Valley Authority, Newman's architects enjoyed an open exchange with engineering design staff. The HDO projects, including direct architectural involvement in engineering works for the first time, were unavoidably entrenched in engineering design issues; this was a necessary matter of expertise. This aspect of the project drew the bulk of the spending and effort in hydroelectric projects; architects did not have training suited to these matters. However, Newman observed: "In general the problem in this type of work is to find a common platform or way of thinking between the Engineer and the Architect." (Newman, c.1956) He determined two fields in which architecture could operate successfully and effectively. Obviously, the buildings associated with the dams – turbine halls, offices and control facilities, workshops, and so on – belonged to his immediate field of concern. Simple determinants of function and circulation directly influenced planning, and a consultative process was involved to produce ar-

chitectural products sensitive to the "technological requirements of gear and power reticulation." Referring to the design of powerhouse buildings: "The case is a problem of scale and order similar to the large single roomed edifices of the past, but restricted to engineering structures, site, etc." (Newman, c.1956) The rapidity required of the hydroelectric programme demanded structures simply and quickly assembled on site. In comparison with the civil engineering costs of earthworks and dam construction and the obvious electrical engineering costs, the architectural budget was rather insignificant; however, as a stand alone operational budget it was very generous, allowing architects serious flexibility and experimentation in both their design work and their choices of materials. For Newman, an architect's role was minimal in the sense of his or her singular impact on a power station site. However, he rendered that role as vital in a collaboration; as engineering solutions developed as aesthetic decisions, the architect became responsible to taking a resolution in built form, and preparing it as a spectacle for consumption by the nation via media mechanisms. In this sense, the addition of beauty to structure was fundamentally important. (Newman, 1959: 71) On this subject he wrote:

"However much an architect may have succeeded in producing a sound building satisfying all the requirements of his client, the ensuing work will contribute little to raise the status of the profession. The general public can only perceive the visual, and in the visual the emotional content is paramount." (Newman, 1952a: 22)

In the case of hydroelectric design works, this involved determining the architectural elements most readily manipulated, suggesting through monumental scale the power of a site. By coordinating the massing of architectural elements, the public received a gracious and powerful image marking national progress, a consequence of the effort of sons and husbands. The development of that image by a sustained influence over the aesthetic consideration of engineers remained the architect's most challenging yet rewarding function in the HDO. So successful were both the role and the open communication between professions that the HDO became the primary designers of public structures whose visual impact was important, over other engineering work groups not including architects.

Maraetai Hydroelectric Power Station (Waikato River, 1946-1952) was New Zealand's first project in which architects were active and integrated members of the design team. The first public power project specifically conceived as a necessity for New Zealand's sustained modernisation, Maraetai would

generate enough power to prevent the country experiencing certain power shortages. This factor meant that construction solutions had to be simple and fast. However, this did not prevent a more profound series of considerations from taking place, these established as precedents for all the power station projects to follow Maraetai from the HDO drawing boards.

In his 1952 article 'Beauty in Engineering', published in the Wellington Architectural Centre journal *Design Review*, Newman wrote: "Works, striking in their forms and of a strange but exciting rhythm, can at present be seen in some of the large hydro-electric constructions built by the Ministry of Works." He saw in the Waikato River power stations shapes of an "amazing likeness to some of the monasteries built since the 10th century on the Greek islands in the Ægean Sea," specifically referring to and illustrating Simopetra on Mount Athos. The restless and elemental images of the transformer platform and the penstocks inscribed with the lines of scaffolding and incompleteness, "reminds us of the fantastic perspectives of the Piranesi Brothers [sic] conceived during the time of the Baroque in Italy." These engineering elements could remain visible; their completion, necessary for the station to function, would hide the historical allusions Newman understood to be operating in this power station. Its historicity prompts, for Newman, serious contemplation:

"There is much matter for thought in these gigantic projects beside their engineering functions and problems which in themselves are of a magnitude without parallel in New Zealand. Our engineers are proud of their work, and rightly so. But is it only the material side of their designs that they are proud of? Does one think only of kilowatts when confronted with such engineering works?" (Newman, 1952b: 88-89)

Contemporaneous to this article is another, 'Social Factors in Architecture and Their Implications for New Zealand', in which images of Alexander Vesnin's powerhouse of the Dneproges Project in the Soviet Union demonstrates "[one] of the outstanding examples of contemporary industrial design." Praising the perfect application of the elements of architecture ("The room behind this impressive wall must be very beautiful") he ventures to ask: "Is it not the transition into architecture of ideas on electrification and industrialisation?" Newman clearly read this hydroelectric project, likely known from his Moscow years, in terms of its signification of electricity and industrialisation. (Newman, 1952a: 16) This building was an architectural consequence of a politically driven electrification programme; Newman's citation

of the project delivered to New Zealand architects a pure lesson in their potential contribution to hydroelectric architecture. Likewise, Maraetai was important as an expression of these political, or at least ideological, imperatives. As rapidly as the designers and constructors could force the elements of the project into shape, media produced newsreels and articles describing the heroic work of men building New Zealand's newest power stations. While the population absorbed the power and beauty of their project, they saw its architecture.

Of the four hydroelectric power stations designed during Newman's eight-year tenure in the HDO, Roxburgh Power Station (Clutha River, 1948-1956) was the final and most striking. The Roxburgh site is, quite literally, powerful, both in its significant generating capacity and in its authority as an image of electrification in New Zealand. The Roxburgh project was developed in response to ongoing electricity shortages experienced in the South Island, with smaller regional stations unable to cope with the Island's increasing dependence on electricity with increasing industrialisation following the War. Once tapped, the proposed site would produce enough electricity not only to quell the current difficulties in power supply but which would easily provide for twenty years' development. Roxburgh was thus a 'project' in the full meaning of the word, a plan resulting in over-abundance of modern energy, electricity rendered utopian as the building project became a promise of better urban, industrial and domestic environments.

The completed hydroelectric dam and powerhouse was the largest in New Zealand, and remedied all South Island power shortages until the late 1960s, when industrial development necessitated the addition of further power stations to the national grid. An internationally relevant public works project, it is an expression of both architectural power and the power of architecture. As a site, it demonstrates a resolution of the relationship between "pure design" and the technological considerations of the highly trained engineers searching for electrical solutions. The engineering features found resolution in an overall image of power transformed and translated into architectural expression. Architecturally, Roxburgh is the most comprehensive of Newman's designs, developing a synthesis of architectural, electrical, and engineering concerns.

While urban environments remain electricity's largest consumers, the landscape is the source of electrical production. Between these two zones of capital interaction, the architecture of power continues to address the importance of electricity to the modern nation. The implementation of a national electrical grid, articulating a network of productive sites,

brought to a logical conclusion the colonial practices of mapping, territorialisation, and infrastructural development that marked the initial cultural and environmental experiences of nineteenth century New Zealand. The 'national grid' is an abstract representation of the relationship between the country's population and its electrically productive territory; it is a mechanism of acculturation, with landscape rendered cultural by the values imposed upon it. Roxburgh marks the maturation of a modern approach to the built environment in New Zealand, both in its production capacity and in architectural synthesis with engineering concerns. It further marks a conclusion to the narratives of progress and hope that accompanied the earliest post-War power station projects, defined as they were by an architectural response to social ideology. The HDO's architecture programme receives little discursive attention, historical commentary focussing on the political and social investment of these public projects and their engineering feats. Newman established the way for electricity's cultural, idealistic, and political meaning to receive attention as architectural form, providing the will to electrify with a currency in architecture. HDO architects subsequently produced architecture for visual apprehension; it is image-architecture in the sense that the scale and proportion applied to each project conveys power. From Maraetai, they established a clear contribution architects could make to the development of infrastructure; refining the profession's role, in that circumstance, as bearer of political and cultural values, architects were capable of communicating through the built environment in a way for which the engineer is ill equipped. Newman, and his successors, reinforced this position in each project. Through consultation and understanding of the particular requirements of both architecture and engineering on the part of each, the architect could manipulate the engineered environment to bear a message of power.

Fig. 1 – Maraetai Power Station, F H Newman and the NZ Government Architect, 1946-1952; photograph by Andrew Leach, 1999.

Fig. 2 – Whakamaru Power Station, F H Newman and the NZ Government Architect, 1949-1954; photograph by Andrew Leach, 1999.

Fig. 3 – Turbine Hall Interior, Whakamaru Power Station, F H Newman and the NZ Government Architect, 1949-1954; photograph by Andrew Leach, 1999.

Fig. 4 – Roxburgh Power Station, F H Newman and the NZ Government Architect, 1948-1956; photograph by Andrew Leach 1999.

KEYWORDS

Electrification, New Zealand, F. H. Newman/1900-64, Power Station

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NOTES

¹ His projects from this time include the Trade-Union Building of the Locomotive Factory in Orsk, the Central Trade-Unions Council Workers' Club in Theodesia, Crimea, the Railway Works Main Entrance Buildings in Kusnetz, Siberia, the Main Entrance Buildings for the Copper Refineries in Balkash, and the Main Entrance Buildings for the 'Stalin' Motorcar Works in Moscow.

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